

Spectrochemical studies on the reaction products of zinc(II) ion with 1,1-dicyanoethylene-2,2-dithiolate in presence of some nitrogen bases

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A number of new mixed ligand complexes of zinc(II) ion have been synthesized by the reaction of zinc nitrate in aqueous/aqueous ethanolic medium with potassium 1,1-dicyanoethylene-2,2-dithiolate ($K_2i\text{-MNT}$) in presence of ammonia, pyridine (py), 2,2-bipyridine (bipy) or 1,10-phenanthroline (*o*-phen), having the compositions, $ZnL_2(i\text{-MNT})$ [$L = NH_3/py$] and $Zn(L-L)_n(i\text{-MNT})$ [$L-L = bipy/o\text{-phen}$, $n = 1, 2$]. The complexes are non-electrolyte in DMSO. Infrared spectral studies suggest unidentate bonding behaviour of NH_3 and py and bidentate chelating behaviour of $i\text{-MNT}^{2-}$ ion, bipy and *o*-phen in their complexes. Octahedral coordination around Zn^{II} ion in these complexes has been proposed.

The coordination chemistry of transition as well as non-transition metal dithiolates has been an area of interest for several years^{1,2}. The role of dithio ligands has been explored in the design of many electrically conducting molecular solids³. In addition, dithiolates find a number of industrial and biological applications^{2,4}.

Among 1,1-dithio ligands, 1,1-dicyanoethylene-2,2-dithiolate ion shows exciting coordination properties by virtue of its chelating and bridging behaviour. The chelating nature of $i\text{-MNT}^{2-}$ ion has been found in its binary and ternary complexes of transition as well as non-transition metals^{1,2}. It also acts as binucleating agents in its hetero-bimetallic complexes⁵. We reported earlier⁶ the reaction of ethylenediamine with $K_2Zn(i\text{-MNT})_2$ and $K_2Cd(i\text{-MNT})_2$ which yielded mixed ligand as well as ionic complexes. The reaction of Ni^{II}/Cu^{II} ions in aqueous solution with $K_2i\text{-MNT}$ in presence of neutral mono- or bidentate nitrogen bases resulted a series of mixed ligand complexes involving nitrogen and sulphur donors. Prior to our report, McCleverty *et al.*⁷ obtained a series of mixed 1,1- and 1,2-dithio complexes of cobalt and iron. But, there is no report on the mixed ligand complexes of zinc(II) ion involving 1,1-dithiolate and neutral nitrogen bases.

Here we report our studies on the reaction products of zinc(II) ion in aqueous/aqueous ethanolic solution with $K_2i\text{-MNT}$ in presence of neutral mono- or bidentate nitrogen bases.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data and stoichiometry of the complexes reveal the formation of mixed ligand complexes of Zn^{II} ion involving neutral nitrogen bases and $i\text{-MNT}^{2-}$ ion (Table 1). The complexes are insoluble in water and common organic solvents but slightly soluble in coordinating solvents (cold/hot) such as DMSO and DMF, while $Zn(NH_3)_2(i\text{-MNT})$ is insoluble in almost all common organic as well as coordinating solvents. The electrical conductance values of the complexes are consistent with non-electrolytic nature⁸. The complexes decompose above 250° except $Zn(NH_3)_2(i\text{-MNT})$ which decomposes at 190°.

Ir spectra : The *ir* spectra of the mixed ligand complexes have been interpreted in the light of earlier investigations⁹⁻¹¹ on transition metal dithiolates. The $i\text{-MNT}^{2-}$ ligand ion may be described by resonating structures in its complexes as shown in Fig. 1. Each of the moieties in the

Table 1. Analytical data and molar conductance values of mixed ligand complexes

Compd	Colour	Decomp temp °C	Zn% Found/ (Calcd)	$\Lambda_M \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$
$Zn(NH_3)_2(i\text{-MNT})$	Yellow	190	27.09 (27.29)	-
$Zn(py)_2(i\text{-MNT})$	White	280	18.20 (17.97)	9.23
$Zn(bipy)(i\text{-MNT})$	Yellow	299	18.50 (18.07)	8.42
$Zn(bipy)_2(i\text{-MNT})$	White	292	13.10 (12.62)	7.81
$Zn(o\text{-phen})(i\text{-MNT})$	White	>300	16.78 (16.94)	3.21
$Zn(o\text{-phen})_2(i\text{-MNT})$	Yellow	>300	11.42 (11.55)	5.75

Each of the moieties in the

Fig. 1

complexes undergoes particular vibrations and contributes certain peaks to their ir spectra. The electron delocalization in the chelated $i\text{-MNT}^{2-}$ ring leads to the coupling of vibrational modes so that few bands in ir spectra represent pure vibrations. The ir spectra of the mixed ligand complexes display characteristic stretching frequencies associated with $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$, $\text{C}=\text{C}$, $\text{C}-\text{S}$ and $\text{M}-\text{S}$ from $i\text{-MNT}^{2-}$; aryl ring vibrations with metal-heterocyclic nitrogen vibrations from py, bipy and $o\text{-phen}$ and amine vibrations with metal-amine nitrogen vibrations from ammonia.

The $\nu_{\text{C}\equiv\text{N}}$ band appearing at 2195 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at 2200 cm^{-1} in $\text{K}_2i\text{-MNT}$, is observed in the range $2181\text{--}2200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the mixed ligand complexes. In all the complexes definite splitting of this peak is observed, which reflects a lower symmetry for these complexes. The $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{C}}$ absorption, which in most of the complexes appears as a doublet ($1310\text{--}1410\text{ cm}^{-1}$), is close to that observed in the free ligand (1370 cm^{-1}), which implies some delocalization of the π -electron out of the $\text{C}=\text{C}$ bond. The observed stretching frequencies of $\text{C}\equiv\text{N}$ and $\text{C}=\text{C}$ suggest that resonance form (a) (Fig. 1) is more dominant in the mixed ligand complexes of $i\text{-MNT}^{2-}$ ligand ion. A band at 960 cm^{-1} with a shoulder at 985 cm^{-1} on the higher frequency side is observed in the ir spectrum of $\text{K}_2i\text{-MNT}$ due to $=\text{CS}_2$ group. The corresponding band in the mixed ligand complexes are found in the range $924\text{--}957\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}}$ band occurring in the spectrum of $\text{K}_2i\text{-MNT}$ at 860 cm^{-1} , appears at $845\text{--}875\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes, indicating symmetrical bonding of both the sulphur atoms to metal ions. Similar bonding behaviour of $i\text{-MNT}^{2-}$ ion is reported¹¹ in $\text{K}_2[\text{Ni}(i\text{-MNT})_2]$, where a single $\nu_{\text{C}-\text{S}}$ band is observed at 900 cm^{-1} . Heterocyclic ring vibrations in the mixed ligand complexes due to py, $o\text{-phen}$ and bipy appear in the ranges $421\text{--}430$ and $625\text{--}630\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively.

The ir spectra of the mixed ligand complexes contain bands characteristic of coordinated neutral nitrogen bases as reported earlier, indicating bonding through the basic nitrogen atom(s)¹⁰. The non-ligand bands observed in the regions $342\text{--}395$ and $255\text{--}320\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the spectra of mixed ligand complexes are tentatively assigned¹⁰ to $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{N}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M}-\text{S}}$ modes respectively.

Based on the above discussion polymeric structures for $\text{Zn}(\text{L}_2/\text{L-L})(i\text{-MNT})$ [$\text{L} = \text{NH}_3/\text{py}$, $\text{L-L} = \text{bipy}/o\text{-phen}$] and octahedral structures for $\text{Zn}(\text{L-L})_2(i\text{-MNT})$ complexes are tentatively proposed. The polymeric structures are also supported by their insolubility and high decomposition temperatures.

Experimental

All chemicals were of AnalaR or equivalent grades and used as such. $\text{K}_2i\text{-MNT}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was prepared by literature procedure⁹.

Synthesis of complexes : Mixed ligand complexes of zinc with 1,1-dicyanoethylene-2,2-dithiolate and nitrogen

bases were isolated by one of the following methods.

$\text{Zn}(\text{NH}_3)_2(i\text{-MNT})$ was formed when $\text{K}_2i\text{-MNT}$ (5 mmol) dissolved in water (50 ml) was added with stirring to an aqueous solution (50 ml) of hydrated zinc nitrate (5 mmol) containing slight excess of ammonia which made the precipitated $\text{Zn}(\text{OH})_2$ soluble.

The white curdy precipitate of $\text{Zn}(\text{py})_2(i\text{-MNT})$ was obtained by mixing aqueous solution (20 ml) of $\text{K}_2i\text{-MNT}$ (5 mmol) to an aqueous solution (80 ml) containing hydrated zinc nitrate (5 mmol) and pyridine (2.5 ml). The curdy precipitate turned into fine particles after stirring the mixture for 20 min.

$\text{Zn}(\text{L-L})(i\text{-MNT})$ [$\text{L-L} = \text{bipy}$, $o\text{-phen}$] complexes were precipitated by reacting an aqueous solution (25 ml) of $\text{K}_2i\text{-MNT}$ (5 mmol) with an ethanolic solution (50 ml) containing hydrated zinc nitrate (5 mmol) and bipy/ $o\text{-phen}$ (5 mmol). $\text{Zn}(\text{L-L})_2(i\text{-MNT})$ [$\text{L-L} = \text{bipy}$, $o\text{-phen}$] complexes were prepared in a similar manner by reacting hydrated zinc nitrate, bipy/ $o\text{-phen}$ and $\text{K}_2i\text{-MNT}$ in 1 : 2 : 1 molar ratio respectively.

All the complexes were washed with water, alcohol and ether and dried under reduced pressure over CaCl_2 .

Metal and sulphur were analysed by literature procedures¹² after destroying the organic matters. C, H and N were determined microanalytically. The molar conductance of the complexes (in DMSO at 10^{-3} to 10^{-4} M) was measured with a WTW conductivity meter. Ir spectra (nujol/KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 983 spectrophotometer.

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